

1 **Control of TOP1 by HPV E6.**

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6 We measured total transcription in cells over-expressing the papillomavirus E6 gene that has described
7 functions in binding and inactivation of p53 for discovery of novel E6 associated cellular functions. We
8 demonstrate here control of *Top1* by HPV E6. This was a conserved property of HPV E6 across type: for
9 both HPV16 E6 and for HPV84 E6.

10 Citations

11 1. Reijns, M.A., Parry, D.A., Williams, T.C., Nadeu, F., Hindshaw, R.L., Rios Szwed, D.O., Nicholson,
12 M.D., Carroll, P., Boyle, S., Royo, R. and Cornish, A.J., 2022. Signatures of TOP1 transcription-associated
13 mutagenesis in cancer and germline. *Nature*, 602(7898), pp.623-631.

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